

LINGUISTIC SHIFTS IN UNIVERSITY STUDENTS WHEN THE TARGET LANGUAGE BECOMES THE MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13995602>

Abstract: This article examines linguistic shifts in university students when the target language becomes the medium of instruction. Linguistic and methodological foundations of teaching include the presentation of methodological foundations of teaching (goals, objectives, patterns, content, methods, means, etc.) in their inextricable connection with language/culture and the nature of communication as a social phenomenon.

Key words: linguistic and methodological foundations, training, professional competence, linguistic personality, knowledge, skills, abilities.

The relevance of the topic is due to obvious contradictions between the existing system of university training of students of different specialties in a foreign language and the needs dictated by the main directions of reforming higher education: bringing it into line with the requirements of modernity, internationalization, qualitative transformation and renewal, an obligatory component of which is a foreign language; between the awareness of the need to develop the ability of future specialists to form knowledge in a specialty in a foreign language, accumulate and synthesize it with their existing knowledge and, on this basis, generate new knowledge in a specialty that would contribute to scientific and economic progress.

First of all, let us characterize "foreign language" as an academic discipline. A specific feature of a foreign language is its pronounced communicative nature. A foreign language serves as a means of communication, a means of receiving and transmitting information about the surrounding reality, and as such it is considered both in the process of its study and in the process of language training of students. The communicative approach is aimed at developing the ability to practically use the language being studied, to correlate its units, forms and structural organizations with the communicative functions they perform. Thus, one of the linguistic features of university students, when the target language becomes a means of instruction, is the communicative approach that stimulates the speech-thinking activity of students. Another feature is that language acts as both a means and a goal of language training. The student learns the easiest language tools, which up to a certain point serve as the goal of

training, and then uses them to learn more complex language tools, that is, these tools themselves become learning tools. Another feature is the ratio of knowledge and skills in studying this subject, since a foreign language requires the same large volume of skills and abilities as practical disciplines, and at the same time no less knowledge than the exact sciences. Thus, mastering a foreign language and developing the intellectual sphere are an ontologically unified process, and the task of teaching foreign speech as a means of communication remains incomplete without the task of teaching a foreign language as a means of mental activity - searching for answers and solutions, defining concepts, formulating judgments, inferences, generalizations, that is, a sequence of intellectual acts. The goals of developing the intellectual sphere on the basis of linguistic features in university students, when the target language becomes a means of teaching, are:

activation of mechanisms of independent intellectual activity

development of speech-
thinking activity

speech-
thinking skills

general
methods of
thinking

cognitive skills
and processes

learning skills

Thus, in the process of interconnected language training in four types of speech activity, students acquire the skills not only to build a variety of actions, but also to carry out reflexive control and consciously evaluate the methods and results of the speech activity. Within the framework of language training of students, not only communicative-speech tasks are solved, but also the necessary educational skills are formed. On this basis, the ability for reflexive regulation of actions arises, which, one way or another, manifests itself in speech activity, contributing to the conscious assimilation of its norms.

Thus, the study of linguistic features of university students, when the target language becomes a means of instruction in universities, allows us to draw a number of conclusions:

1. The specificity of language training is predetermined by the pronounced communicative nature of the language itself. That is, communicative skills can potentially act as a tool that allows you to use the communicative features of the language in order to expand the intellectual and cognitive sphere of students.

2. A feature of the language training of university students is its professional focus, connection with core professional interests. Professionally oriented training of students, including linguistic features of university students, when the target language becomes a means of instruction, is carried out on the basis of modeling the future professional activity of a specialist. Therefore, the content of language training of university students should be filled with additional professionally significant scientific information, allowing students to deepen their professional competence.

3. An important feature of the linguistic training of students is the ratio of knowledge and skills necessary for a future specialist. According to this feature, a foreign language occupies an intermediate position between the disciplines of the humanitarian, natural science cycle and the disciplines of aesthetic, professional training, since a foreign language requires the same large volume of skills and abilities as practical disciplines and at the same time no less knowledge than the exact sciences. Hence the conclusion about the integrative nature of knowledge, skills and abilities of language training.

4. From the motivational standpoint, a feature of linguistic training of university students, when the target language becomes a means of instruction, is the need for students to acquire self-control and self-assessment skills in order to increase its effectiveness. The psychological and pedagogical essence of self-control and self-assessment lies in the ability to correlate and evaluate the obtained result with a certain sample. This self-control is aimed mainly at determining the success of linguistic training in relation to the goals defined by the program and the educational tasks adopted by students at each stage of training.

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